

**PHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT
OF INDIVIDUAL VALEOLOGICAL COMPETENCES****Kholliyeva Shakhlo Bakhtiyorovna**

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of physiological factors in the formation and development of valeological competencies of a person, their place and significance in the educational process from a scientific and pedagogical point of view. Valeology, as a science aimed at studying human health, life activities and a healthy lifestyle, serves to form a culture of healthy living in students and pupils. The article extensively covers the healthy psychophysiological development of a person, the characteristics of the body's activity in the younger periods, the influence of stress and emotional states, and the role of pedagogical and psychological approaches in the development of valeological competencies.

In the 21st century, improving human health and the quality of life has become a global pressing issue. Today, raising a healthy, spiritually mature and physically fit person is a strategic goal of every state. That is why the valeological approach in the education system - that is, pedagogical activities aimed at forming a culture of healthy living - occupies an important place.

Valeology (Latin valeo - "to be healthy") studies the preservation and strengthening of a person's ability to live a healthy life, physiological capabilities. The development of valeological competencies in a person requires not only theoretical knowledge, but also knowledge of the physiological laws of the organism and their application in practical activities. Therefore, this article comprehensively analyzes the physiological foundations, pedagogical factors and practical methods of developing valeological competencies in a person.

Valeological competence is a person's ability to form a healthy lifestyle, maintain their health, and manage their physiological and psychological balance. It is manifested not only as knowledge, but also as practical skills and values.

In pedagogy, the competency approach is based on the integral development of the individual, that is, the ability to apply knowledge, skills, and competencies in life. Therefore, valeological competence is the ability of a person to:

- be able to understand and assess one's own health;
- forming a healthy lifestyle;
- stress management;
- engage in moderate physical activity;
- includes skills for maintaining mental balance.

The collaboration of teachers, parents, and society is crucial in building these competencies.

Physiological foundations of the development of valeological competencies. The healthy functioning of the human body depends on the harmonious functioning of all its physiological systems. When the neurophysiological, cardiovascular, respiratory, endocrine, and nervous systems work in harmony, the individual's mental stability and the effectiveness of educational activities increase.

Nervous system and emotional balance - The nervous system controls all physiological processes in a person. Since the nervous system is not yet fully formed in children and adolescents, their emotional reactions are strong but unstable. Therefore, in valeological education, it is useful to use exercises to stabilize the psychophysiological state, relaxation techniques, and music therapy methods.

The importance of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems - Physical activity is an important component of valeological competence. The normal functioning of the heart, the harmony of the circulatory and respiratory systems determine the energy metabolism of a person, and therefore, cognitive activity. Therefore, such simple habits as physical exercises, morning exercises, walks in the fresh air form the physiological basis for the valeological development of a person.

The physiological importance of sleep and nutrition - Sufficient sleep creates the basis for the recovery of the central nervous system, the active functioning of memory and attention processes. Proper nutrition, in turn, coordinates the activity of all body systems. Therefore, instilling a culture of proper nutrition in students is considered an integral part of valeological competence.

The effectiveness of the valeological approach is associated with taking into account physiological factors in the educational process. During each lesson, it is necessary to take into account the student's physical condition, level of attention, and fatigue indicators.

Interactive methods: The use of interactive methods such as "Brainstorming", "Cluster", "Network Diagram", and "Healthy Life Motto" in teaching valeological knowledge encourages students to think actively.

Practical exercises: In biology, anatomy, and physical education classes, observing the body's activity, measuring heart rate, conducting breathing exercises, and practicing proper sitting and walking postures allow students to connect physiological knowledge with practice.

Parental cooperation Supporting healthy lifestyle habits in the family environment is the most effective way to strengthen valeological competencies. Educators should promote seminars for parents, recommendations on healthy eating, and stress-reducing exercises.

Physiological factors are of decisive importance in the entire life activity of a person. The human body, as an energy system, relies on a regular balance of movement, breathing, nutrition and rest. Physiological stability also directly affects a person's social relationships. Stress, insomnia, malnutrition, physical inactivity disrupt a person's emotional state, reduce attention and make the learning process ineffective. A healthy physiological state, on the contrary, increases a person's motivation, strengthens willpower and stimulates creativity. Therefore, it is necessary to create healthy living conditions in educational institutions, equip gyms, and organize recreation and rehabilitation zones.

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